

A NEW APPROACH TO TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Annotation. After independence, the attention to the mother tongue and its teaching increased, and the main goal was to teach school-aged youth well and to make them love it through new methods. The education of an independent child, including the education of the mother tongue, is a complex and varied process, and its implementation in a way that meets the requirements of the time depends on many factors.

Keywords: native language class, Uzbek language, methodology, tasks of this group, mechanical and meaningful exercises, questions.

In this case, state policy (conditions created by the state), educational tools (textbook, manual quality, level), methods and tools (technical, physical, etc.) used to instill their content into the mind of the student, the professional skills (personality enthusiasm, conscience, etc.), student's ability (mental, memory), learning, education are of decisive importance of the person (teacher) who implements education, [5].

In fact, the problem is a bit different, as you know, how to organize a native language class that is taught every year, at every level? How to interest the student through non-standard exercises?

This problem has attracted the attention of language teachers for a long time. The diversity of his solution search is reflected in the use of bright, unusual didactic material, and in the use of non-standard tasks.

The methodology of teaching the mother tongue assumes the theoretical acquisition of a certain part of the Uzbek language, including phonetics and phonology, lexicology and phraseology, word formation and etymology, grammar - morphology and syntax, stylistics, as well as orthography, graphics, orthography is an important basis of mother tongue methodology. Phonetics and phonology in relation to graphics serve as a basis for the development of literacy teaching methods and the formation of elementary reading skills. Phonetics and graphics are also important in mastering spelling rules based on the phonetic principle. Husnikhat methodology is based on graph theory. Knowledge of lexicology means vocabulary work at school (conducting various exercises on words with similar and opposite meanings, working on polysemous words, their meaning colors) is very important for proper organization.

It is known that today there are more than a hundred types of interactive methods, most of which have been tested and have given good results. Effective results can be achieved in the lesson by using the widely used methods – “Cluster”, “Brainstorming”, “Continue”, “Presentation”, “Blitz survey”, “Problem situation”. “Reverse test”, “Wheel of Mind” methods are used in the part of the lesson to ask about the passed topic, “Insert”, “Pinboard”, “Step by step”, “Boomerang” technologies in the part of explaining the new topic, in the part of strengthening the topic Graphic organizers such as Venn Diagram, Fishbone, Why?, How?, Concept Chart, Lily Flower, and Concept Analysis, T-Table, Resume. The use of “Sunflower” method for homework helps to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the knowledge of students.

In addition to the above-mentioned interactive methods, didactic games such as “Yes... no”, “Find the owner of the definition”, “Who am I?”, “Domino” can be used in the native language and literature classes. During the game, students behave freely and want to show their knowledge. As a result, the student gains confidence and determination. Learns to engage in debate. He is used to justifying his opinion. The age and level of education of students should be taken into account.

The most crucial aspect of communication in a foreign language is making up sentences and using them. Grammar plays an important role in avoiding composing erroneous sentences. The grammar exercises in Uzbek textbooks for school pupils are beneficial in utilizing grammar structures. Uzbek textbooks consist of the following three types of grammar exercises (the classification developed by Paulson, 1971) [4, 167-208]

Mechanical exercises:

The textbook mostly contains mechanical exercises which restrict the pupils' answer to one. The main shortcoming of the mechanical exercises is that it is not difficult for pupils to do exercise even though they do not understand the sentences.

Communicative exercises require learning the submitted rule by using it in normal communication. These exercises require a continual communication and the pupils use rules for several times. For instance, if we want the pupils to learn the prepositions of place, we can demonstrate the picture of a street with images of the buildings as well as the names of the buildings. The pupils are asked to describe the street using the prepositions as next to, opposite, in front of, near. Another example for communicative exercises can be handouts with the words tall-short, sad-happy, young-old and with the pictures of people suitable to the description of the words. And pupils can make the comparative and superlative form of the words looking at the picture.

Above mentioned mechanical and meaningful exercises outnumber communicative exercises in English textbooks. First two exercises limit the introduction and the usage of special grammar structures. To clarify, working with the mechanical and meaningful exercises might not assist pupils in learning grammar structures. By contrast, communicative exercises which involve pupils in real communication can help them learn to utilize the structures in real communication. In my opinion, teachers should create communicative exercises on special grammar structures on par with mechanical and meaningful exercises and provide with the opportunity of using them in communication.

LINGUISTIC “ASSISTANTS”

These are questions, the purpose of which is to activate the mental activity of students in repeating previously acquired knowledge. Unexpected question formulation and non-traditional content serve as a good incentive to complete tasks. Answering questions, making unique small “discoveries” in the field of linguistics, schoolchildren are convinced of the practical meaning of knowledge of the Russian language, the academic subject itself opens a new path for them. Behind the external simplicity of the questions lies a serious linguistic content: students must explain linguistic facts in “scientific language”. Thus, the main thing in performing these tasks is not to recognize the facts of the language, but to explain them.

The tasks of this group include:

- problems of a problematic nature (choosing one of several options, distinguishing between two correct options, comparing options);
- questions of an entertaining nature (they are based on a non-linguistic situation: questions-jokes, questions-riddles, “unexpected” or “children’s” questions).

Today, the use of non-standard new types of dictation in native language classes is widespread.

Non-standard dictations of this type include:

"To Fill" Dictations:

- edit sentences and texts saturated with elements of the same type as much as possible (speech errors, incorrect words and constructions);
- choosing linguistic units of the same type (synonyms, similar words, etc.) to the given one - "who is more?" according to the principle;
- exercises with a multiple-choice answer (choosing the correct option from several proposed ones or removing an event from the series according to the "additional third" principle).

"Subject" (terminological) dictations. Write the dictated phrases in one word.

Linguistic dictation

The science of language. Graphic designation of sound in writing. The part of the word before the root. A definition expressed by a noun. Water, water to water ... Blue sky, look at the sky, look far ...

Literary dictation

Artistic exaggeration. The structure of the work of art. Short story. Literary memories. Plagiarism.

Mathematical dictation

An elongated square. An equilateral rectangle. A line that bisects an angle. 1000 grams. 100 kilograms. 1000 kilograms. 1000 meters.

Historical dictation

An armed attack by one country against another country. People power. Absence of any power. The spread of economic and political influence of one country on another country. Politics of intimidation, violence, suppression.

By using non-standard exercises, the quality of students' knowledge, their ability to acquire knowledge, as well as cognitive and motivational activity, will significantly increase. And they go to classes not for grades, but for educational and cognitive motives - for their own growth, self-improvement. Pupils actively participate in educational dialogue in the classroom, think, analyze, reasoned arguments, are not afraid to make mistakes and admit them. But the most important thing is that students and the teacher should feel comfortable in such classes.

In conclusion, the 21st century requires educated people to act independently in all types of comprehensive information, to solve many problems of production and civil behavior.

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